

Potential zoonotic pathogens in urban red squirrels: A bacteriological pilot survey in a Japanese urban park

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Abstract

Urban wildlife typically reduces vigilance and increases tolerance toward humans. However, human-wildlife interactions, such as direct feeding, may facilitate the transmission of zoonotic pathogens. This bacteriological pilot survey analyzed 20 palm and 20 rectal swab samples collected from 18 Eurasian red squirrels inhabiting an urban park to investigate their bacterial flora. Most bacteria isolated from the palm swabs were resident microbiota (e.g., *Staphylococcus sciuri*). *Escherichia coli* was isolated from 12 of the 20 swab samples, and one isolate was identified as serotype O25, which may be associated with pathogenic *E. coli*. However, no other major pathogens, including *Pasteurella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp., were observed. Although this was a pilot study, the findings suggest a possible pathogen presence in Eurasian red squirrels inhabiting an urban park in Japan. Further investigation of specific virulence determinants, particularly with respect to *E. coli*, is required to assess the risk of pathogen transmission in an urban park in Japan.

Keywords: human-wildlife conflict, supplemental feeding, urban wildlife, zoonosis

Introduction

While urbanization generally hurts biodiversity, urban environments can provide alternative habitats for wildlife (Grimm et al., 2008). To adjust or adapt to urban environments, some species have modified their phenotypes, including their life history, physiology, and behavior (Grimm et al., 2008; Samia et al., 2015). For example, in several species, the distances at which animals escape from approaching predators, a common behavioral measurement of fearfulness and tolerance to humans, are shorter in urban individuals than in rural conspecifics (Samia et al., 2015). This behavioral change allows urban wildlife to survive in urban environments.

Behavioral changes in urban wildlife can lead to human-wildlife conflicts and increase the risk of diseases, as reduced distance between urban wildlife and humans facilitates contact (Uchida et al., 2024). Particularly, the transmission of diseases between urban wildlife and humans, pets, and livestock has become an increasing concern in public health (Bradley et al., 2007; Hassell et al., 2017). Given these risks, to effectively manage public health, pathogens of various taxa have been investigated. However, potential zoonotic pathogens should be investigated across different regions and species to enable more effective public health in urban areas.

Although arboreal squirrels are typically sensitive to habitat fragmentation and isolation (Rodríguez & Andrén, 2001), they are found in urban parks and green spaces worldwide (Uchida et al., 2019; Krauze-Gryz et al., 2021). Urban squirrels modify their behavior, such as reducing vigilance and habituation to humans (Uchida et al., 2019). In addition, squirrels occasionally approach visitors to receive supplemental food (Krauze-Gryz et al., 2021). Direct feeding interactions are observed globally where humans and wildlife coexist. However, these interactions may bring increased risk of zoonotic pathogen transmission, particularly when the wildlife are pathogen reservoirs.

Our previous findings in an urban park in Obihiro, Hokkaido, Japan, revealed that squirrels habituate to humans and often receive direct feeding from park visitors throughout the year (Uchida et al., 2019; Takahata et al., 2023). Therefore, the potential transmission of zoonotic pathogens is of concern. However, while pathogens have been detected in ticks removed from squirrels in Europe (Dwużnik-Szarek et al., 2024), pathogen surveys in Eurasian red squirrels remain limited in Japan. Therefore, the present study aimed to provide insight into zoonotic pathogens in Eurasian red squirrels. We conducted a bacteriological pilot survey by isolating bacteria from palm and rectal swabs collected from Eurasian red squirrels inhabiting an urban park to gain initial insights into their bacterial flora.

Materials and methods

The study area was an urban park in Obihiro, Hokkaido, Japan (42°54'18"N, 143°11'14"E) located within a residential area, with an average of 35.96 ± 1.82 visitors per hour (mean \pm SE). Park visitors frequently provide walnuts and pine seeds to squirrels, and direct feeding has been observed (Fig.1) (Takahata et al., 2023). Squirrels were captured in this park using live traps (Model RB-2, Sakae Industry Co., Ltd., Niigata, Japan) baited with walnuts and pine nuts in May and October 2022 and May 2023. Trapping was conducted from 6:00 AM to 10:00 AM with continuous monitoring to minimize stress. Each captured squirrel was identified individually using ear tags. After recording the fundamental information of captured individuals (e.g., sex, maturity, body weight, and reproductive status), we collected rectal and palm swabs. In total, 20 rectal and 20 palm swabs were collected from 18 individuals using sterile swabs (E-MS60, Eiken Chemical Co., Ltd., Tochigi, Japan). Three individuals (two females and one male) were captured in May 2022, 13 (five females and eight males) in October 2022, and four (all males) in May 2023. Two individuals were recaptured in October 2022 and May 2023. However, because of the limited sample size, swab samples were treated as independent observations, and detection is reported at the sample level rather than the individual level. Most squirrels were identified as adults based on the development of their external genitalia or their previous capture one year earlier. Although the age classes were unknown in some squirrels, all individuals weighed over 300 g (mean \pm SE: 351 ± 27 g), indicating that none of them were juveniles. The capture and handling were approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of the Nippon Veterinary and Life Science University (2023S-34).

The swab samples were refrigerated immediately after collection and transported to Fujifilm Vet Systems Co., Ltd. (Tokyo, Japan) within two days for commercial diagnostic bacterial analysis. Palm swabs were processed for routine bacterial culture and detection of *Pasteurella* spp., and rectal swabs were used for stool culture and for the isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. General bacteria and *Pasteurella* spp. were identified using aerobic culture tests, followed by species identification using mass spectrometry. For aerobic bacterial isolation, TSA2 5% sheep blood agar and BTB agar, and Chocolate II agar (all from BD, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) were used. BTB lactose agar (BD, USA), TWIN Plate 11 (SS + CT-SMAC; Kyokuto Pharmaceutical Industrial Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan), TCBS agar (Kyokuto Pharmaceutical Industrial Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan), and modified *Campylobacter* blood agar (Kohjin Bio Co., Ltd., Saitama, Japan) were used to isolate enteric bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Vibrio* spp., and *Campylobacter* spp. *E. coli* isolates

were identified using mass spectrometry combined with manual methods following stool culture. No fixed number of colonies was specified for testing because colony size varies among taxa; whenever possible, a single representative colony isolate was selected.

O antigen serotyping of *E. coli* was performed using a commercially available pathogenic *E. coli* immune serum set (No. 1 set (N); Denka Seiken Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan), which is the standard reagent for *E. coli* serotyping in Japan. Serotyping was conducted to screen for potential pathogenic strains; however, no additional genetic analyses, such as toxin gene (LT, ST) detection or sequence typing, were performed. The cultivation of *Campylobacter* spp. and O antigen serotyping were performed under optimal conditions using appropriate media and incubation temperatures.

The target bacterial panel was selected based on previous studies highlighting zoonotic bacteria at the human–wildlife interface in urban environments. In addition to characterizing resident aerobic microbiota in Eurasian red squirrels (Olah et al., 2022), we focused on culturable bacteria relevant to direct contact and fecal–oral transmission in urban parks, including *E. coli*, *Pasteurella* spp., and *Campylobacter* spp.

Figure 1. Hand feeding a walnut to a Eurasian red squirrel.

Results

Table 1 provides detailed information on the bacteria isolated from swab samples. Twelve species of bacteria were isolated from 15 of 20 palm swab samples. The most frequently detected bacteria were *Staphylococcus sciuri* and *Pseudomonas* spp., including *P. putida* (each detected in 25.0% of palm swab samples), followed by *Acinetobacter* sp. (15.0%), *Bacillus* sp. (15.0%), *Pantoea agglomerans* (10.0%), *Enterobacter* spp. (10.0%; including *Ent. cloacae*), *Arthrobacter* sp. (5.0%), *Erwinia* sp. (5.0%), *Ewingella americana* (5.0%), *Hafnia alvei* (5.0%), *Paenibacillus* sp. (5.0%), and *Stenotrophomonas* sp. (5.0%). No *Pasteurella* spp. were detected. From the rectal swabs, only *Escherichia coli* was isolated in the stool culture; *E. coli* was detected in 12 of 20 rectal swab samples (60.0%). Among the *E. coli*-positive rectal swab samples (n = 12), serotype O25 was identified in a single colony isolate from one sample collected from a female captured in October 2022. No *Campylobacter* spp. or other enteric pathogens were isolated from any rectal swabs. Given the limited sample size, these findings should not be interpreted as evidence of their absence in the study population. In addition, no obvious differences in bacterial detection were observed between sexes or among sampling seasons, although these comparisons were exploratory due to the limited sample size.

Table 1. Sample-level detection of bacteria isolated from palm and rectal swab samples of Eurasian red squirrels categorized by sex, year, and month.

Palm swab		Sex		Year		Month	
Bacteria	Total	Female	Male	2022	2023	May	October
<i>Staphylococcus sciuri</i>	25.0	28.6	23.1	26.7	20.0	15.4	42.9
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	25.0	28.6	23.1	33.3	0.0	0.0	38.5
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>	5.0	0.0	7.7	6.7	0.0	7.7	0.0
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	20.0	28.6	15.4	26.7	0.0	0.0	30.8
<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp.	15.0	0.0	23.1	13.3	20.0	14.3	15.4
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	15.0	28.6	7.7	13.3	20.0	42.9	0.0
<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	10.0	28.6	0.0	13.3	0.0	14.3	7.7
<i>Enterobacter</i> spp.	10.0	28.6	0.0	13.3	0.0	0.0	15.4
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	5.0	14.3	0.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.	5.0	14.3	0.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Arthrobacter</i> sp.	5.0	14.3	0.0	6.7	0.0	14.3	0.0
<i>Erwinia</i> sp.	5.0	0.0	7.7	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Ewingella americana</i>	5.0	0.0	7.7	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Hafnia alvei</i>	5.0	0.0	7.7	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Paenibacillus</i> sp.	5.0	14.3	0.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Stenotrophomonas</i> sp.	5.0	0.0	7.7	6.7	0.0	0.0	7.7
<i>Pasterulla</i> spp.	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Rectal swab		Sex		Year		Month	
Bacteria	Total	Female	Male	2022	2023	May	October
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	60.0	57.1	61.5	53.3	80.0	71.4	53.8
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Discussion

Understanding the presence of pathogens, including zoonotic agents, in urban areas is crucial for public health within the One Health framework (Hassell et al., 2017). To date, several pathogens have been detected in Eurasian red squirrels. Ruyts et al. (2017) detected *Borrelia* spp., which are agents of Lyme borreliosis, recognized as tick-borne diseases, in squirrels killed by road traffic in Flanders, Belgium. Dwużnik-Szarek et al. (2024) demonstrated the transmission risks of *Rickettsia* spp. and *Babesia* spp. from ticks feeding on Eurasian red squirrels living in urban parks in Warsaw, Poland. In contrast to these pathogen-focused studies, Olah et al. (2022) characterized the cultivable resident aerobic microbiota of Eurasian red squirrels under wild and captive conditions, and did not find clear differences between environments. In the previous study, *S. sciuri* and *E. coli* were the most frequently detected taxa, detected in 12 of 20 individuals (60%) and 9 of 20 individuals (45%), respectively. These findings are consistent with the present study, in which the majority of bacteria detected from palm and rectal swabs were interpreted as components of the resident microbiota rather than primary or obligate pathogens. Together, these results from the present and previous studies suggest that *S. sciuri* and *E. coli* represent common aerobic bacterial taxa in Eurasian red squirrels across different environmental contexts.

In the present study, bacteria associated with opportunistic infections were isolated from palm and rectal swab samples. The risk is likely low because these bacteria are widely distributed in nature. However, previous studies have reported that *S. sciuri* can cause exudative epidermitis in piglets (Chen et al., 2007) and septic shock and urinary tract infections in humans (Horii et al., 2001; Stepanovic et al., 2003). In addition, *S. sciuri* has been linked to antimicrobial resistance through the *mecA* gene, which is associated with the acquisition of methicillin-resistance in *Staphylococcus* spp. (Wu et al., 2001). To better understand the pathogenic and antimicrobial resistance potential of these bacteria, continuous monitoring of pathogens in urban wildlife, including Eurasian red squirrels, and further genetic analyses (e.g. the *mecA* gene) would be valuable.

Escherichia coli serotype O25 was isolated from one rectal swab sample. Although the individual showed no signs of deteriorating health (weight of 430 g; the heaviest among all individuals), this serotype is often considered a highly virulent serogroup of pathogenic *E. coli* (Poolman and Wacker, 2016). Several case reports in Japan have implicated *E. coli* serotype O25 in food poisoning incidents (Sonoda et al., 2021). Therefore, direct contact between humans and squirrels, as well as between pets and squirrels, could theoretically facilitate transmission in urban parks. However, only serotype information is insufficient to determine pathogenic potential. Pathogenic potential should be assessed

by profiling virulence-associated genes, such as adhesins (*pap*, *afa/dra*, and *sfa*) characteristic of extraintestinal pathogenic *E. coli* (ExPEC), using PCR-based approaches (Sarowska et al., 2019). In addition, PCR-based detection of genes encoding heat-labile and heat-stable enterotoxins (LT, ST) would be necessary, as serogroup O25 has historically been associated with enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) (Watando et al., 2021).

As our bacteriological survey was preliminary, the sample size was limited. In addition, bacterial identification was based on single-colony isolates whenever possible, and a fixed number of colonies per sample was not systematically screened. Consequently, rare or co-occurring bacterial strains may have been missed, particularly for *E. coli*, which is known to exhibit within-host strain diversity. These limitations indicate that the absence of additional *E. coli* serotypes, as well as *Pasteurella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp., in the present study should not be interpreted as evidence of their absence. Larger sample sizes and broader microbial surveillance are required to gain a better understanding of pathogen presence in Japanese urban parks.

The present study provides bacteriological information on the presence of resident microbial taxa in urban Eurasian red squirrels. These findings indicate that wildlife inhabiting urban parks in Japan may carry bacteria with zoonotic potential in proximity to humans, including *E. coli* serotype O25. In Japan, *E. coli* belonging to sequence type 131 (ST131), which is a lineage frequently associated with extraintestinal pathogenic *E. coli*, has been reported from sika deer *Cervus nippon* inhabiting urban parks (Ikushima et al., 2023). These findings highlight that potentially pathogenic *E. coli* lineages can occur in urban wildlife in Japan. Therefore, direct wildlife feeding, which increases physical contact between humans and wildlife, could theoretically facilitate pathogen transmission. However, evidence for active transmission or the presence of specific virulence determinants remains limited, and further investigation is required.

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